

STUDYING THE ANTIANEMIC ACTIVITY OF THE PREPARATION FOLIC ACID

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Relevance. Anemia is a group of diseases characterized by a decrease in the number of circulating red blood cells and (or) hemoglobin (Hb) in a unit of blood volume below the normal level for a given age and gender. Today, the relevance of the anemia problem remains high: every fourth person in the world suffers from anemia, and women and children are especially affected. Anemia is a common symptom of a wide range of diseases, including malignant tumors, and requires attention due to its severe consequences for health and quality of life, especially in Africa and Southeast Asia. Prevention and treatment of iron deficiency is one of the most important health problems in many countries around the world. In the treatment of anemia, folic acid plays a key role, ensuring the process of formation of blood cells (erythrocytes) when there is a lack of iron in the body. Stimulates erythropoiesis, participates in the synthesis of nucleic and amino acids, purine and pyrimidine bases, in the metabolism of choline and histidine.

The aim of the study: to study the bioequivalence of the drug "Folic acid" - tablets of 1 mg (p. 010724, s.g. 08.26) manufactured by Navbahor Sanoat LLC, Uzbekistan in comparison with the analog drug "Folic acid" - tablets of 1 mg (p. 31091024, s.g. 102027). Borisov Plant of Medical Preparations OJSC, Republic of Belarus.

Material and methods: acute toxicity of the drugs was studied on 60 white mice of mixed sex weighing 19-21 g. Folic acid and the reference drug Folic acid were administered as an aqueous suspension once intragastrically to mice at doses of 1.0 mg/kg; 1.25 mg/kg; 1.5 mg/kg; 2.0 mg/kg and 3.0 mg/kg. After completion of the experiment, the median lethal dose (LD50) was determined. The specific activity of the compared drugs was studied on white rats of both sexes weighing 160-175 g. The phenylhydrazine model (Ya.Ya. Sokolovskaya) was used to select agents that have a positive effect on erythropoiesis. The studies were conducted on white rats, phenylhydrazine was administered intramuscularly daily for 4 days at a dose of 20 mg/kg of body weight. Then, over the course of 10 days, the test drugs were administered intragastrically.

Results. The experiments showed that after a single intragastric administration of the compared drugs, LD50 of Folic acid manufactured by Navbahor Sanoat LLC, Uzbekistan and Folic acid manufactured by Borisov Plant of Medical Preparations OJSC, Republic of Belarus was more than 3.0 mg/kg.

Specific activity experiments show that when administering Folic acid manufactured by Navbahor Sanoat LLC, Uzbekistan and Folic acid manufactured by Borisov Plant of Medical Preparations OJSC, Republic of Belarus in doses of 500 mcg/kg, the hemoglobin level, erythrocyte content and hematocrit in the blood of experimental animals were higher by 21.2%; 53%; 66%, respectively, compared to the control group. The obtained results indicate the presence of equivalent antianemic action of the compared drugs.

Conclusions. The study of bioequivalence of the drug Folic acid - tablets of 1 mg (p. 010724, p. 08.26) manufactured by Navbahor Sanoat LLC Uzbekistan, in comparison with the drug Folic acid - tablets of 1 mg (p. 31091024, p. 10.27) manufactured by Borisov Plant of Medical Preparations

OJSC, Republic of Belarus, in terms of acute toxicity and specific activity showed that the drugs are biologically equivalent.